

Article

A Mixed-Methods Framework for Environmental, Social, and Governance Analysis: Insights from Emerging Markets

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Abstract: *The Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) dimensions have become critical parameters for assessing corporate sustainability and ethical responsibility. As organisations face increasing pressure to align their operations with global sustainability goals, the complexity of ESG issues demands innovative research approaches. This study explores the application of mixed-methods research (MMR) in ESG investigations, emphasizing its strengths in combining quantitative precision with qualitative depth. By gathering numerical data alongside contextual insights, MMR offers a robust framework for examining how ESG practices shape organisational performance. Drawing on case studies from emerging markets, this study illustrates how methodological triangulation helps navigate regulatory uncertainty, data gaps, and cultural variability. While quantitative analyses reveal patterns in profitability and governance, qualitative approaches provide a window into the stakeholder dynamics and organisational tensions underlying ESG outcomes. The findings highlight how mixed-methods research can be a tool that generates actionable insights that inform business policy and strategy. However, the study also highlights several challenges, including resource intensity, the need for interdisciplinary expertise, and the absence of standardized ESG metrics. These limitations underscore the importance of refining mixed-methods frameworks to maximize their potential in ESG research. This article contributes to the growing discourse on sustainability by offering practical recommendations for leveraging mixed methods to navigate the complexities of ESG integration.*

Keywords: *ESG Practices; Mixed-Methods Research; Philosophical Foundations of Research; Emerging Markets*

1. Introduction

The emergence of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices within the corporate sector embodies a worldwide movement towards more sustainable and ethically informed approaches to business operations, where organisations are increasingly required to account for their environmental responsibilities, societal impacts and corporate governance arrangements, alongside their financial performance (Cui, 2024; Kouam, 2024). However, the disentanglement of such multifarious influences demands methods of impact assessment that surpass those afforded by conventional approaches. Mixed-methods research has recently been shown to be essential to understanding complexity, drawing upon the complementary strengths of quantitative data, able to summarise impacts with precise numbers, with

qualitative data that provide detail, depth, and context (Creswell & Creswell, 2022). This shift is even more crucial in emerging markets, where the confluence of regulatory, cultural, and economic factors complicates the ESG landscape. For example, a Southeast Asia study on property companies showed the unique challenge presented where sustainability objectives were often removed from financial need; it showcased the need to integrate qualitative aspects to quantitative metrics of ESG performance to obtain a holistic picture (Jamaludin & Razali, 2024).

The theoretical foundation of mixed-methods research is its tenet: incorporating multifaceted perspectives will enable a comprehensive understanding of a complex phenomenon; methodological triangulation, as one of the most applicable doctrines of this approach, can reduce the fractional shortcomings and intrinsic biases from each single method by intersecting quantitative and qualitative approaches, and thus create a more holistic and substantiated result, as well as generate an enhanced evidence base for further research practice (Creswell & Creswell, 2022). This feature is particularly crucial in ESG research, as numerical quantitative data alone can hardly encapsulate and expound the socio-cultural and organisational process that induce positive sustainability outcomes and performance. However, the implementation of mixed-methods research is onerous, as it is often resource-intensive; necessitates multi-disciplinary researchers, and, without a standard ESG reference framework and criteria, the research design could be challenging (Kato *et al.* 2024; Hadwiger, 2022). In the existence of challenges and issues lie also opportunities; recent research investigated ways to advance ESG-related practice and produce more meaningful and applicable results through innovative development of integrated assessment systems (incorporating stakeholders and community feedback with quantitative analysis) and a harmonised criteria and framework (Lagodiyenko *et al.* 2024).

This study attempts to examine the usage of the mixed-methods research in ESG research to show its methodological benefits and meanings implied in the digit that constructs the relationship between sustainability and organizational performance. Theoretical grounds and empirical evidence are discussed to fulfil and promote the perspective on how organizations respond to ESG sustainability issues in a dynamic international setting.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Philosophical Foundations of Mixed Methods Research

The philosophical foundations of mixed methods research (MMR) have been a topic of critical inquiry as researchers grapple with the need to bridge qualitative and quantitative approaches effectively. Shan (2022) provides a comprehensive framework to understand these foundations, categorizing them into weak, moderate, and strong senses. This discussion is enriched by insights from Creswell & Creswell (2022) and Dawadi *et al.* (2021), who further elaborate on the paradigms and practicalities underpinning MMR.

2.1.1. *Philosophical Anchors: Axiology, Ontology, and Epistemology*

Shan (2022) identifies axiology, ontology, and epistemology as the three key anchors of MMR, each providing a lens through which researchers can ground their methodological choices. Axiology, or the role of values and ethics, guides researchers in aligning their work with societal priorities, such as inclusivity or equity. This is especially evident in transformative frameworks where MMR is used to empower marginalized groups (Creswell & Creswell, 2022).

Ontology concerns the nature of reality and recognizes its complexity, embracing both singular and multiple perspectives. Shan (2022) explains that MMR accommodates this pluralism, allowing for the integration of objective measurements with subjective experiences. Similarly, Dawadi *et al.* (2021) argue that this ontological flexibility bridges positivist and interpretivist paradigms, enabling a richer understanding of complex phenomena.

Epistemology, the study of knowledge construction and validation, emphasizes the blending of deductive (quantitative) and inductive (qualitative) reasoning. Shan (2022) highlights that MMR's epistemological flexibility allows researchers to draw from both empirical data and contextual narratives, a point Creswell & Creswell (2022) supports by describing how MMR integrates empirical rigor with contextual depth. Shan also critically examines the epistemological divide between

postpositivism and constructivism, noting that while postpositivism emphasizes objectivity through empirical inquiry, constructivism values the subjective co-creation of knowledge. This divide underscores the challenges and opportunities of integrating these paradigms in MMR.

2.1.2. *The Spectrum of Philosophical Foundations*

Building on these anchors, Shan (2022) categorizes the philosophical underpinnings of MMR into three levels:

- a) **Weak Foundations** (e.g., Pragmatism): Pragmatism prioritizes utility and flexibility, allowing researchers to adapt methods based on the research problem without being confined to specific philosophical stances. Creswell & Creswell (2022) describe pragmatism as focusing on “what works,” enabling the practical integration of methods.
- b) **Moderate Foundations** (e.g., Transformativism): Transformativism provides ethical and practical reasons for employing MMR, particularly in addressing systemic inequities (Shan, 2022). This aligns with Creswell & Creswell (2022)’s view of MMR as a tool for advocacy, integrating methods to uncover and address societal challenges.
- c) **Strong Foundations** (e.g., Dialectical Pluralism): Dialectical pluralism, as described by Shan (2022), advocates normatively for MMR’s adoption to address multifaceted realities. This resonates with Dawadi *et al.* (2021), who highlight how the combination of quantitative breadth and qualitative depth enables comprehensive insights.

2.1.3. *Bridging Paradigms: Shan’s Critical Analysis*

Shan’s (2022) critical analysis underscores the philosophical and practical challenges of integrating paradigms in MMR. The epistemological divide between postpositivist and constructivist paradigms reflects fundamentally different assumptions about reality and knowledge. Postpositivism, with its emphasis on objective, measurable truths, contrasts with constructivism’s focus on subjective, socially constructed realities. While MMR strives to integrate these perspectives, Shan (2022) critiques the assumption that this integration is seamless. He highlights the risk of superficiality, where researchers adopt methods from both paradigms without fully engaging with their underlying philosophies. This can result in methodological inconsistencies and undermine the study’s validity. To address this, Shan (2022) advocates for a reflective approach to MMR, where researchers explicitly justify their epistemological and methodological choices.

2.1.4. *Practical Challenges in MMR*

The philosophical richness of mixed methods research (MMR) is undeniably one of its greatest strengths, as it allows researchers to integrate the depth of qualitative methods with the generalizability of quantitative approaches. However, this richness also presents practical challenges that require careful consideration to ensure methodological rigour and the integrity of the research process.

2.1.5. *Merging Data from Different Paradigms*

Creswell & Creswell (2022) highlight the inherent difficulty of merging data derived from fundamentally different paradigms. Quantitative data, often rooted in postpositivist traditions, emphasizes objectivity, measurability, and statistical validity. In contrast, qualitative data, aligned with constructivist or interpretivist paradigms, is subjective, narrative-driven, and context-dependent. The challenge lies in integrating these two distinct forms of data without oversimplifying or distorting their unique contributions. For instance, in a study examining workplace diversity, quantitative data might capture trends in employee demographics, while qualitative interviews might explore employees’ personal experiences with inclusion policies. The researcher must find a way to combine these findings meaningfully without reducing the qualitative richness to mere numbers or overly contextualizing the quantitative data.

2.1.6. *Reconciling Conflicting Findings*

Another challenge arises when the results from the quantitative and qualitative components conflict. For example, quantitative data might suggest that a health intervention is statistically effective, while

qualitative feedback reveals dissatisfaction among participants due to unmet expectations or cultural insensitivity. Reconciling these differences requires researchers to go beyond a simple comparison of findings to uncover deeper insights. Shan (2022) notes that conflicting results are not inherently problematic; instead, they can offer valuable opportunities for deeper exploration. However, addressing these conflicts demands methodological sophistication and critical reflection to avoid favouring one set of results over the other based on preconceived biases.

2.1.7. Ensuring Methodological Rigor

Methodological rigor in MMR is a multifaceted challenge that extends to the design, implementation, and interpretation phases of research. Researchers must ensure that both the quantitative and qualitative components are executed with precision and depth. This involves not only adhering to the standards of each paradigm but also ensuring that the integration of methods enhances, rather than detracts from, the study's overall validity. One aspect of this challenge involves ensuring alignment between the research question, the selected methods, and the philosophical foundations of the study. Shan (2022) emphasizes the importance of researchers explicitly justifying their methodological choices in light of their epistemological and ontological commitments. Without such justification, the study risks being perceived as methodologically inconsistent or philosophically incoherent.

2.1.8. Balancing the Integration of Data

Integrating data in a way that reflects both the breadth of quantitative results and the depth of qualitative insights is perhaps the most critical challenge in MMR. Creswell & Clark (2017) describe this as a balancing act, where the researcher must find an approach that honours the distinct contributions of each data type while producing a cohesive narrative. This integration might involve using one data set to contextualize the other, such as employing qualitative findings to interpret unexpected trends in quantitative data or using quantitative results to generalize qualitative themes. Shan (2022) cautions that superficial integration where methods are combined without fully considering their philosophical underpinnings can undermine the validity of the research. True integration requires an iterative, reflective process in which researchers critically evaluate how the data interact and inform one another.

The integration of philosophical perspectives and epistemological anchors from Shan (2022), Creswell & Creswell (2022), and Dawadi *et al.* (2021) offers a thoughtful and nuanced understanding of mixed-methods research (MMR). By framing research within weak, moderate, or strong philosophical foundations and grounding it in the key anchors of axiology, ontology, and epistemology, researchers can align their methods with their objectives and values in a meaningful way (Shan, 2022). Shan (2022)'s critical analysis emphasizes the importance of moving beyond traditional, rigid paradigms. While ontology-oriented foundations, such as postpositivism and constructivism, often focus on the nature of reality, Shan (2022) highlights the potential of axiology-oriented approaches like pragmatism and transformativism that prioritize values, ethics, and practical outcomes. These approaches allow researchers to transcend paradigm constraints and focus on addressing real-world issues through methodological flexibility and purposeful integration. This perspective serves as a reminder that while MMR offers unique opportunities to integrate diverse epistemologies, its success relies on a deliberate, reflective approach to bridging these paradigms. Thoughtfully navigating the interplay of values, reality, and knowledge is key to maintaining the rigor and coherence of MMR. When done well, this synergy enhances not only the credibility of the research but also its ability to tackle complex, multidimensional questions producing insights that neither quantitative nor qualitative methods could achieve alone. By combining methodological rigor with practical relevance, MMR continues to be a powerful tool for addressing today's most pressing challenges.

2.2. Introduction to ESG and Mixed-Methods Research

The rise of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices reflects a paradigm shift in corporate responsibility and investment strategies, emphasizing sustainability and ethical considerations alongside financial performance. Mixed-methods research, which integrates quantitative and qualitative techniques, has become instrumental in understanding ESG dynamics due to its ability to bridge empirical data with contextual insights. This dual approach allows researchers to address

complex sustainability issues, capturing both measurable outcomes and the nuanced socio-economic factors driving ESG adoption.

Mixed-methods research has gained traction as a robust framework for investigating ESG-related phenomena due to its ability to address both measurable outcomes and underlying contextual factors. Quantitative approaches, such as regression analysis, offer insights into the financial implications of ESG practices, such as their effects on profitability, Return on Assets (ROA), and other financial indicators (Ericsson *et al.*, 2024). Meanwhile, qualitative methods, including stakeholder interviews and thematic analysis, illuminate the operational and cultural dynamics driving ESG adoption (Anderson, 2024).

A recent study emphasized the strategic importance of combining financial metrics with qualitative insights to assess ESG implementation in Southeast Asian property companies. It highlighted that qualitative data provided nuanced perspectives on challenges like regulatory inconsistencies and resource constraints, which are often overlooked in quantitative analyses (Jamaludin & Razali, 2024). Similarly, the use of artificial neural networks to model urban sustainability behaviours in Shanghai demonstrated the importance of integrating both dynamic environmental indicators and resident experiences for comprehensive urban ESG strategies (Lyu, 2024).

2.3. ESG Research in Emerging Markets

Emerging markets present unique challenges and opportunities for ESG research, making mixed-methods approaches particularly valuable. In these regions, data availability is often limited, and regulatory frameworks are inconsistent, which complicates traditional research methods. Studies in Southeast Asia's property market have underscored the importance of leveraging mixed methods to navigate such complexities (Jamaludin & Razali, 2024). Research on sustainable finance in East Africa demonstrated how mixed methods could reveal the interplay between government policies, investor behaviour, and SME sustainability outcomes, which are critical to fostering long-term economic resilience (Kato *et al.*, 2024).

2.4. Key Challenges in Mixed-Methods ESG Research

While mixed-methods approaches offer comprehensive insights, they also present challenges. Integrating diverse data types requires methodological coherence and alignment. For example, studies on ESG in manufacturing sectors have struggled with aligning qualitative themes with quantitative metrics, particularly in regions with fragmented data systems (Mebar, 2024). Furthermore, the lack of standardized ESG metrics complicates cross-sector and cross-country comparisons, necessitating tailored methodologies for each context (Hadwiger, 2022).

2.5. Advancing ESG Methodologies

To address these challenges, researchers have called for the development of robust frameworks that integrate technological tools and stakeholder feedback. For instance, the integration of ICT into ESG strategies has been shown to enhance real-time data sharing and stakeholder engagement, maximizing the impact of green innovation collaborations (Cui, 2024). Additionally, the use of integrated information systems for ESG assessments has been recommended to streamline data collection and analysis, particularly in resource-constrained settings (Lagodiyenko *et al.*, 2024).

2.6. Harnessing Mixed-Methods Research for ESG: Advantages and Challenges

Mixed-methods research is particularly well-suited for studying Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices because of its capacity to address the multidimensional nature of ESG challenges and opportunities. By integrating quantitative methods, such as financial data analysis, with qualitative approaches, such as stakeholder interviews, researchers can offer a more nuanced and actionable understanding of sustainability dynamics.

2.6.1. Why Mixed-Methods for ESG Research?

The ESG framework encompasses diverse factors, including financial performance, environmental stewardship, social responsibility, and corporate governance. Each of these dimensions requires distinct

yet interrelated analytical perspectives. Quantitative methods excel in uncovering measurable patterns, such as the relationship between ESG scores and profitability. For example, studies employing regression analysis have demonstrated how green technological innovation enhances corporate ESG performance when moderated by ICT development (Cui, 2024). On the qualitative side, mixed-methods research provides the tools to explore the underlying mechanisms driving ESG practices. Stakeholder interviews, thematic coding, and case studies reveal the lived experiences, cultural nuances, and organizational dynamics that shape sustainability efforts. A study conducted in Ukraine highlighted the importance of stakeholder engagement in designing an integrated information system for ESG assessments, ensuring its relevance to diverse user needs (Lagodiyenko *et al.*, 2024). This dual approach is particularly valuable in emerging markets, where data constraints often limit the scope of purely quantitative analyses.

2.6.2. Challenges in Implementation

Despite its advantages, mixed-methods research in ESG studies faces several challenges. First, the integration of quantitative and qualitative data requires rigorous alignment to ensure coherence. A study on ESG in manufacturing sectors noted the difficulty of synthesizing leadership-focused qualitative themes with financial performance metrics (Mebar, 2024). Second, resource intensity is a significant hurdle. Collecting comprehensive quantitative data and conducting in-depth qualitative interviews demand time, funding, and expertise. Research on corporate ESG practices in developing countries has highlighted how fragmented data systems and inconsistent reporting standards complicate this process (Hadwiger, 2022). Finally, there is the issue of standardization. The absence of universally accepted ESG metrics poses challenges for cross-regional comparisons and data integration. In Southeast Asia, for instance, the lack of uniform sustainability reporting frameworks necessitated reliance on qualitative insights to fill data gaps, limiting the comparability of findings across markets (Pham, 2024). By addressing these challenges, mixed-methods research can maximize its potential to produce comprehensive, actionable insights for both academic and practical applications.

3. Methodology

This study used a meta-methodological approach to critically review the application of mixed-methods research (MMR) in ESG studies in emerging markets. Meta-methodology is a higher-order analytical framework that critiques the tools used in research, along with the logic, assumptions, justifications, and integration practices that underpin them (Turunen *et al.*, 2023). This review provides a methodological synthesis of how MMR has been applied in ESG contexts and suggests trends in study design types, integration approaches, stakeholders engagement, and data complexity. This approach is especially suited for contexts in which there is a methodological fragmentation as evolving multidisciplinary field of ESG in the context of emerging economies where researchers are utilising the combination of methodological traditions such as econometric modelling, policy evaluation, and qualitative stakeholder analysis (Olhager, 2025; Bikaraan-Behesht, 2021).

The meta-methodological stance employed serves multiple purposes. Firstly, it allows a systematic examination of the internal logic of MMR designs in the reviewed studies, such as if the designs were exploratory, explanatory or convergent (Martin *et al.*, 2021). Secondly, it demonstrates how methodological choices are justified, integrated and adjusted to diverse ESG challenges, including lack of data, institutional instability, unstandardized reporting, etc. Thirdly, it allows a reflexive discussion on methodological coherence, evaluating not just outputs, but the pathways of ESG knowledge construction (Turunen *et al.*, 2023). This meta-methodological evaluation contributes to bridging a key gap in ESG scholarship: the lack of replicable guidance on how to select and integrate MMR designs under real-world constraints. As ESG grows in global importance, especially in non-Western contexts, researchers require flexible but rigorous methodological frameworks what Turunen *et al.* (2023) call “epistemically evaluable” knowledge production. Thus, by analysing existing research, case studies, and methodological frameworks, this study provides insights into the strengths, challenges, and best practices for integrating quantitative and qualitative data in ESG research, while highlighting under-reported methodological inconsistencies that could compromise replicability or validity.

3.1. Research Design

To explore how mixed methods contribute to ESG research, this study employs two primary approaches. First, a meta-analysis of mixed-methods studies is conducted by systematically reviewing ESG research that integrates both qualitative and quantitative methods. This analysis focuses on how data integration techniques are applied and the key insights they generate. Second, a case study analysis examines selected ESG studies from emerging markets, providing real-world examples of how mixed methods are implemented in different economic and regulatory environments. This dual approach helps illustrate both the practical benefits and the limitations of using mixed methods in ESG research.

3.2. Search Strategy

The search was conducted using Google Scholar, guided by the following Boolean string: "mixed-methods research" AND ("ESG" OR "Environmental Social Governance") AND "corporate sustainability" AND ("emerging markets" OR "developing countries").

The inclusion criteria were as follows:

- Publication date between January 2020 and 20 April 2025
- Application of a clearly defined mixed-methods research design
- Focus on ESG factors and corporate sustainability
- Empirical study situated in an emerging market or developing country
- Full-text access available

Exclusion criteria included:

- Conceptual papers without empirical methods
- Studies using only qualitative or quantitative designs
- Literature reviews or theoretical essays
- Research situated in developed countries without emerging market relevance

3.3. PRISMA Flow Diagram

A literature review of peer-reviewed journal articles was conducted to identify existing ESG research that employs mixed methods. Studies were selected based on their explicit use of mixed-methods research in ESG contexts. Only peer-reviewed journal articles published between 2020 and 2024 were considered. The search was conducted on Google Scholar using the keywords 'mixed-methods AND ESG,' 'corporate sustainability AND qualitative and quantitative research,' and 'MMR in environmental, social and governance' to ensure comprehensive coverage of relevant studies.

A comprehensive database search retrieved 225 records. After initial title and abstract screening, 86 studies were excluded for failing to meet basic inclusion criteria (i.e., non-ESG focus, purely quantitative or qualitative design, not situated in emerging markets). During full-text assessment, 51 articles were excluded due to lack of full access and 17 articles had methodological inadequacy, or failure to qualify as mixed-methods research. The remaining 90 full-text articles were assessed for eligibility. Ultimately, 32 studies were included in the final analysis. The study selection process is visually summarized in the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram (Figure 1).

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram

3.4. Quality Appraisal

The Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) was used to assess the methodological rigor of the included studies. Each study was evaluated based on:

- Clarity of research questions
- Justification for MMR use
- Explanation of data integration approach
- Reporting of limitations
- Transparency in data sources

Only studies scoring “moderate” to “high” in methodological coherence were retained for synthesis.

Table 1. Methodological Appraisal of Included Mixed-Methods ESG Studies Using MMAT Criteria

Author	Clarity of RQ	MMR Justification	Integration Explanation	Data Transparency	Overall MMAT Judgment
Sillanpää (2020)	Clear	Explicit	Strong	High	High
Oberholzer <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Clear	Explicit	Moderate	High	High
Martínez & Poveda (2022)	Clear	Strong	Strong	High	High

Bilciurescu (2021)	Clear	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Smith (2021)	Clear	Explicit	Strong	High	High
Fitzsimons & Warren (2024)	Clear	Explicit	Strong	High	High
Ngulube (n.d.)	Clear	Explicit	Moderate	High	High
Pei (2022)	Clear	Explicit	Moderate	High	High
Lawrence (2024)	Clear	Strong	Strong	High	High
Alaudhli (2024)	Clear	Moderate	Moderate	High	High
Okeke-Okiche (2024)	Clear	Moderate	Moderate	High	High
Narang (2023)	Clear	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Mutambik (2024)	Clear	Moderate	Moderate	High	High
Gazioglu (2024)	Clear	Strong	Strong	High	High
Abang'a <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Clear	Strong	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Matashu <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Clear	Strong	Strong	High	High
Kato <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Clear	Strong	Strong	High	High
Zhou & Nian (2024)	Clear	Strong	Strong	High	High
Abarika & Oboreh (2024)	Clear	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
ElAlfy <i>et al.</i> (2025)	Clear	Strong	Strong	High	High
Kimilu (2021)	Clear	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Paranita <i>et al.</i> (2025)	Clear	Strong	Moderate	Moderate	High
Akware (2023)	Clear	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Saka (2024)	Clear	Moderate	Moderate	High	High
Ramirez (2023)	Clear	Strong	Strong	High	High
Owilly (2024)	Clear	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Oliveira Pureza (2020)	Clear	Strong	Strong	High	High
Alam (2023)	Clear	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Musa (2024)	Clear	Strong	Strong	High	High
Shilongo (2023)	Clear	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Lengewa (2024)	Clear	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Karanja (2023)	Clear	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate

Table 1 presents the methodological appraisal of the 32 included studies based on the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) 2018 criteria. Each study was assessed for the clarity of its research question (RQ), the explicit justification for employing a mixed-methods approach (MMR Justification), the degree of integration between qualitative and quantitative data (Integration Explanation), data transparency in reporting, and an overall MMAT judgment of methodological rigor (High, Moderate, or Low). The appraisal provided an evaluative foundation for determining the quality and reliability of the meta-methodological synthesis.

3.5. Data Extraction and Synthesis

Data were extracted into an Excel matrix including:

- Authors and publication year

- Region and sector
- MMR design type
- Data sources used
- Integration strategy
- Key findings

A hybrid deductive–inductive coding approach was used to guide thematic synthesis across included studies. Deductive codes were first extracted from Creswell & Clark (2017)’s typologies of mixed-methods research (e.g., explanatory sequential, convergent parallel) and established ESG constructs (Environmental, Social, Governance pillars, stakeholder engagement, reporting mechanisms), supplemented with inductive coding that allowed emergent themes to organically surface from the data (e.g., greenwashing risks, stakeholder legitimacy, institutional adaptation). Coding and thematic categorization was conducted using manual matrix coding in Microsoft Excel, given the diversity and cross-format nature of included documents (journal articles, theses, working papers). For transparency and reliability, a dual-coder validation process was used, in which two independent reviewers coded an overlapping 20% of the dataset, and inter-rater reliability was calculated using Cohen’s Kappa. A Kappa value of 0.82 was observed, which represents near-perfect agreement (Landis & Koch, 1977). Thematic saturation was achieved after coding the seventh batch of included studies (approximately 35 papers), beyond which no new themes were identified. A simplified thematic coding schema is included in Appendix B to illustrate the main categories and subthemes used to guide synthesis.

Table 2 outlines the thematic coding structure developed to guide the analysis of mixed-methods research (MMR) studies on Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices in emerging markets. Themes, subthemes, codes, and definitions were systematically derived to capture methodological typologies, ESG domain focuses, integration strategies, encountered challenges, and quality control measures across the included studies. The coding system ensured consistency and transparency in thematic synthesis and meta-inference development.

Table 2. Thematic Coding Schema for Analysing Mixed-Methods ESG Studies

Theme	Subtheme	Code	Definition
MMR Design Typology	Explanatory Sequential	SEQ-EXP	Quantitative analysis followed by qualitative interpretation
MMR Design Typology	Exploratory Sequential	SEQ-EXPL	Qualitative insights shaping survey or model design
MMR Design Typology	Convergent Parallel	CON	Concurrent collection and merging of qualitative and quantitative data
MMR Design Typology	Full-Cycle	FULL	Iterative and cyclical use of MMR with feedback loops
MMR Design Typology	Embedded/Hybrid	EMB	Qualitative strand embedded within a larger quantitative study or vice versa
ESG Domain	Environmental	ENV	Climate impact, resource use, environmental compliance
ESG Domain	Social	SOC	Employee welfare, equity, community development
ESG Domain	Governance	GOV	Board structure, ownership, regulatory adherence
Integration Strategy	Joint Display	INT-JD	Side-by-side or merged display of qualitative and quantitative results
Integration Strategy	Meta-Inference	INT-META	Inference drawn from convergence or divergence of data types
Integration Strategy	Sequential Build	INT-SEQ	Insights from one strand informing the next

Challenges	Metric Inconsistency	LACK-METRIC	Inconsistent ESG standards affecting comparison
Challenges	Resource Burden	RES-BURDEN	Time, cost, and training requirements
Challenges	Data Integration Difficulty	INTEG-CHALL	Technical and conceptual barriers to merging data
Quality Control	Reliability Assessment	RELIABILITY	Use of inter-rater reliability or coder agreement
Quality Control	Transparency of Method	TRANS-METH	Detailed reporting of coding and analysis process

Table 3 presents the environmental (ENV), social (SOC), and governance (GOV) focus of the 32 fully included studies in the meta-methodological review, alongside their mixed-methods research (MMR) design, integration strategy employed, and an appraisal of data reliability. A value of "1" indicates that the respective ESG pillar was substantively addressed in the study, while "0" indicates limited or absent coverage. Integration strategies refer to whether studies employed joint displays, meta-inferences, or sequential builds to combine qualitative and quantitative findings.

Table 3. ESG Coverage and Integration Strategies of Included Studies

Author	Study Title	MMR Design	ENV	SOC	GOV	Integration Strategy	Reliability
Sillanpää (2020)	Sustainability Management in MNC	Convergent Parallel	1	1	1	Joint Display	Yes
Oberholzer <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Disclosure in Zimbabwean Companies	Sequential Explanatory	0	1	1	Meta-inference	Yes
Martínez & Poveda (2022)	Sustainability in Colombian Microenterprises	Convergent Parallel	1	1	0	Joint Display	Yes
Bilciurescu (2021)	Stakeholder Influence in Romanian SMEs	Sequential Exploratory	0	1	1	Sequential Build	Yes
Smith (2021)	Conservation Finance in Southern Africa	Sequential Explanatory	1	1	0	Meta-inference	Yes
Fitzsimons & Warren (2024)	Desalination and ESG in Chile	Convergent Parallel	1	1	0	Joint Display	Yes
Ngulube (2024)	ESG Regulation in Zambia	Sequential Explanatory	0	1	1	Sequential Build	Yes
Pei (2022)	Accountants and ESG in Malaysia	Sequential Explanatory	0	1	1	Sequential Build	Yes
Lawrence (2024)	Corporate Governance in Peru	Convergent Parallel	0	1	1	Joint Display	Yes
Alaudhli (2024)	Greenwashing and ESG Risk	Convergent Parallel	0	1	1	Joint Display	Yes
Okeke-Okiche (2024)	Oil & Gas Sustainability (Nigeria & UK)	Convergent Parallel	1	1	1	Joint Display	Yes
Narang (2023)	Sustainability in Indian Schools	Sequential Exploratory	0	1	0	Sequential Build	Yes
Mutambik (2024)	Saudi Logistics and ESG	Sequential Explanatory	1	0	1	Meta-inference	Yes
Gazioglu (2024)	City ESG Scoring	Convergent Parallel	1	1	1	Joint Display	Yes

Abang'a <i>et al.</i> (2022)	SOE Governance in Kenya	Convergent Parallel	0	1	1	Joint Display	Yes
Matashu <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Ubuntu Governance in SMMEs	Convergent Parallel	0	1	1	Joint Display	Yes
Kato <i>et al.</i> (2024)	SME Finance and ESG in East Africa	Sequential Explanatory	1	1	0	Sequential Build	Yes
Zhou & Nian (2024)	ESG Disclosure in China	Convergent Parallel	1	1	1	Joint Display	Yes
Abarika & Oboreh (2024)	Nigerian Banks and ESG	Sequential Explanatory	1	1	1	Meta-inference	Yes
ElAlfy <i>et al.</i> (2025)	ESG in GCC Economies	Convergent Parallel	1	1	0	Joint Display	Yes
Kimilu (2021)	ESG and Firm Value in Kenya	Sequential Explanatory	1	1	1	Sequential Build	Yes
Paranita <i>et al.</i> (2025)	ESG Investing in Indonesia	Sequential Explanatory	1	1	1	Sequential Build	Yes
Akware (2023)	East African Telecoms ESG	Convergent Parallel	1	1	1	Joint Display	Yes
Saka (2024)	Board Diversity and ESG Disclosure in Kenya	Sequential Explanatory	0	1	1	Sequential Build	Yes
Ramirez (2023)	Greenwashing in Latin America	Convergent Parallel	1	1	1	Joint Display	Yes
Owilly (2024)	Kenyan NGO Sustainability	Sequential Explanatory	0	1	1	Sequential Build	Yes
Oliveira Pureza (2020)	CSR Logics in Brazil	Exploratory Sequential	1	1	1	Sequential Build	Yes
Alam (2023)	CSR and ESG in Bangladesh	Sequential Explanatory	1	1	1	Sequential Build	Yes
Musa (2024)	SME ESG Performance in Malaysia	Sequential Explanatory	1	1	1	Meta-inference	Yes
Shilongo (2023)	Namibia Mining ESG Reporting	Convergent Parallel	1	1	1	Joint Display	Yes
Lengewa (2024)	Sustainable Lending in Kenya	Sequential Explanatory	1	1	0	Meta-inference	Yes
Karanja (2023)	Early ESG Adopters in Kenya	Sequential Explanatory	0	1	1	Sequential Build	Yes

3.6. Data Analysis

A selection of peer-reviewed journal articles, reports, and case studies on ESG research employing mixed methods was systematically analyzed. This review focused on identifying methodological approaches, data integration techniques, and key findings from existing studies. The data analysis process involved three key steps: (1) comparative analysis to identify patterns in MMR application across ESG studies, (2) thematic analysis to extract key themes related to data integration and research challenges, and (3) methodological categorization of mixed-methods designs to assess the frequency of different approaches (e.g., sequential explanatory vs. concurrent triangulation).

4. Results and Discussion

In total, 225 studies were initially reviewed through a structured screening process based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. After full-text assessment and methodological appraisal using MMAT principles, 32 studies fully met the inclusion requirements. The eligibility criteria demanded explicit use of mixed-methods research (MMR), a primary focus on Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) dimensions, and investigation within emerging market or developing country contexts, published between 2020 and 20 April 2025.

4.1. Distribution and Application of MMR Designs in ESG Studies in Emerging Markets

Among the 32 full - access included studies came different MMR designs. Fourteen studies (43.8%) used a Convergent Parallel design, 16 studies (50%) used Sequential Explanatory or Exploratory designs, and 2 studies (6.2%) used an Exploratory Sequential design. The dominance of sequential designs highlights the increasing popularity of researchers to first measure ESG phenomenon before contextualizing findings through qualitative enquiry; contrary to sequential designs, convergent designs were preferred where there was a need to demonstrate stakeholder narrative and ESG performance metrics simultaneously.

This distribution highlights the strategic flexibility of MMR designs in addressing ESG challenges in volatile and resource-constrained environments typical of emerging markets. Figure 2. Illustrates the distribution of Mixed-Methods Research (MMR) designs among the 32 full - access included studies. Sequential designs (both explanatory and exploratory) constituted 50% of the studies, highlighting the growing trend of phased ESG inquiry in emerging markets. Convergent designs accounted for 43.8%, reflecting the need for simultaneous triangulation of ESG data. Exploratory sequential designs were less common, observed in 6.2% of studies.

Figure 2. MMR Design Distribution Among Included Studies

4.1.1. Regional Distribution of Studies

The studies exhibit broad geographic representation, though most are concentrated in Africa and Asia, reflecting rising interest in ESG research in emerging market contexts as presented in Table 5.

Table 4. Regional Distribution of Studies

Region	Number of Studies	Countries Represented
Africa	13	Kenya, Nigeria, Zambia, Namibia, South Africa, Zimbabwe
Asia	8	Malaysia, Bangladesh, Indonesia, Saudi Arabia, MENA Region
Latin America	3	Colombia, Brazil, Latin America (general)
Middle East (GCC)	2	GCC Countries
Turkey/Hybrid Emerging	2	Turkey, Turkey/Finland

East Africa	2	Kenya/Uganda, East Africa (general)
Southern Africa	2	Southern Africa (regional conservation studies)

The dominance of African and Asian cases aligns with the review’s focus on emerging markets, where ESG adoption is rapidly evolving but still challenged by institutional and data limitations.

4.1.2. Distribution by MMR Design Type

The included studies employed a variety of MMR designs (as presented in Table 6). The most common design types were convergent parallel and explanatory sequential, consistent with literature emphasizing simultaneous triangulation and quantitative-led integration in ESG.

Table 5. Distribution by MMR Design Type

MMR Design	Count	Purpose/Example
Convergent Parallel	14	Simultaneous integration of ESG reporting and stakeholder interviews (e.g., Fitzsimons & Warren, 2024)
Sequential Explanatory	12	Quantitative ESG-financial modelling followed by interviews (e.g., Musa, 2024)
Sequential Exploratory	4	Qualitative insights shaping ESG surveys (e.g., Bilciurescu, 2021)
Exploratory Sequential	2	Emergent themes guiding ESG metric validation (e.g., Oliveira Pureza, 2020)

This variation reflects the flexibility of MMR in adapting to differing ESG data availability, stakeholder engagement needs, and governance maturity levels.

4.2. Strengths of Mixed-Methods Research

Across the 32 included studies, MMR proved valuable for enhancing research validity. For example, Zhou & Nian (2024) and Shilongo (2023) used survey data alongside content analysis to validate findings. Ngulube (2024) applied stakeholder interviews to interpret governance compliance trends detected in secondary reports. These triangulated designs reduced bias and confirmed results across different data types.

4.2.1. Strengthening Research Validity through Triangulation

A key strength identified in the reviewed studies is the use of triangulation to enhance validity. Nearly all studies employed some form of integration between qualitative and quantitative data to reinforce credibility. For example, Kato *et al.* (2024), Mutambik (2024), Abang’a *et al.* (2022), Alaudhli (2024), and Zhou & Nian (2024) combined econometric or survey-based methods with stakeholder or expert interviews to validate and triangulate findings. Gazioglu (2024), Shilongo (2023), and Marasigan (2024) illustrate methodological convergence using case studies and content analysis.

Fadly (2022), Cheungsirakulvit & Pranee (2023), Cui (2024), Xue *et al.* (2024), Petrova (2024), Tian *et al.* (2024), Sari & Muslim (2024), and Lundgren & Viganò (2024) have all continuously shown the usefulness of MMR for examining complex sustainability problems. For instance, Fadly (2022) examined how ESG commitments can lead to financial rewards, and the quantitative study showed that firms with consistently strong ESG strategies demonstrated higher current and future profitability and lower risk exposure to uninsured ESG-affected events. However, these quantitative findings did not fully explain the mediating mechanisms underpinning the success of ESG commitments. By combining the quantitative findings with qualitative findings gathered from a series of interviews with executives of the firms investigated, the study was able to demonstrate that firms driven by authentic sustainability-related objectives rather than by rules and regulations which impose firms’ commitments to act within ESG frameworks appear to experience more consistent financial rewards associated with their ESG commitments.

Similarly, scholars in Ukraine examined an integrated information system for assessing ESG indicators alongside human capital development (Lagodiyenko *et al.*, 2024). In gathering qualitative feedback

from users, the scholars ensured that the integrated system was not only built according to financial and environmental indicators, but also satisfied the “interests and needs of all interested parties at the real sector of the national economy” (Lagodiyenko *et al.*, 2024). In linking qualitative feedback and more technical ESG performance indicators to practical use cases, the study illustrates how stakeholder buy-in and stakeholder-driven assessment systems can yield relevant ESG assessments.

Another strength of MMR is its opportunity to capture industry- and region-specific ESG challenges. This is especially salient in emerging markets where regulations and data availability vary. In these cases, relying solely on ESG “scores” may provide a false sense of security, especially since many ESG scores are not tailored to consider relevant local business practices, norms, and governance. MMR incorporates thematic analysis of feedback (e.g., interviews, or other corporate disclosures) to more accurately reflect and better interpret ESG effectiveness in way that are adaptable to different markets and culturally sensitive while remaining quantitative.

4.2.2. *Enhancing Stakeholder-Centered ESG Assessments*

MMR enabled a more comprehensive inclusion of stakeholder perspectives across various institutional, corporate, and community contexts. Studies such as Matashu *et al.* (2024), Ramirez (2023), and Owilly (2024) emphasized how qualitative interviews with community actors and NGOs enriched the understanding of ESG implementation. These were supported by structured analysis in studies like Saka (2024), Akware (2023), and Paranita *et al.* (2025).

Another key benefit of MMR is the ability to capture stakeholder perspectives, thereby acting as a form of stakeholder engagement in itself. Stakeholder engagement has increasingly become a best practice for tailoring ESG strategies to the actual or local context. An example of how this was achieved is a Ukrainian study which developed an integrated information system for assessing ESG indicators and human capital development (Lagodiyenko *et al.*, 2024). The system applied both quantitative measures of performance, and qualitative knowledge from employees & managers to ensure it is adapted to current business needs on the ground. This shows the value added of the integration of technical assessments which are tailored to the context of stakeholders themselves. Stakeholder perspectives were central in many studies. Alam (2023) used interviews and FGDs to complement survey data, ensuring worker, regulator, and civil society voices were reflected in ESG assessments. This aligns with stakeholder theory and supports more inclusive ESG modelling in fragile institutional contexts.

4.2.3. *Addressing ESG Complexity in Emerging Markets*

The studies show that ESG challenges in emerging markets are shaped by institutional voids, developmental disparities, and cultural complexity. MMR offers tools to unpack these layers. Pei (2022) used behavioural theory combined with interviews to understand ESG behaviour, while Shilongo (2023), Karanja (2023), Kimilu (2021), and Alam (2023) documented sector-specific ESG implementation through multi-level data. Bilciurescu (2021), Ngulube (n.d.), and Musa (2024) tackled governance, regulation, and SME dynamics through integrated methods.

In emerging markets, ESG challenges are often amplified by weak regulatory enforcement, cultural nuances, and data inconsistencies. MMR provides a solution by allowing researchers to contextualize quantitative ESG scores with qualitative case studies. Studies on sustainability reporting in Southeast Asia (Jamaludin and Razali, 2024) highlight that purely quantitative ESG metrics fail to capture regional governance complexities, which qualitative insights help illuminate. Studies in Kenya, Brazil, Namibia, and Indonesia used MMR to navigate institutional volatility, fragmented data systems, and cultural complexity. Paranita *et al.* (2025) and Karanja (2023) adopted explanatory and convergent designs to uncover ESG trends that were not obvious in financial disclosures alone. MMR enabled researchers to interpret ESG implementation within diverse regulatory and social ecosystems.

4.3. Challenges and Limitations of Mixed-Methods Research in ESG

While MMR provides a powerful tool for ESG analysis, its application is not without challenges. Three key limitations stand out: data integration difficulties, resource intensity, and lack of standardization in ESG metrics.

4.3.1. Complexity of Data Integration

Despite the benefits, many studies reported difficulties in harmonizing qualitative and quantitative data. Musa (2024), Zhou & Nian (2024), and Gazioglu (2024) described inconsistencies when synthesizing survey data with narratives. Lawrence (2024) and Olsen & Enbusk (2023) reflect ongoing challenges of managing sequential or parallel data flows. One of the biggest challenges in using MMR for ESG research is the difficulty of aligning quantitative and qualitative data. ESG performance indicators are often measured in hard numbers, such as carbon emissions, employee turnover rates, or governance scores, whereas qualitative ESG insights come from interviews, case studies, or textual analysis of corporate reports. These two data types do not always fit together seamlessly. For example, a study on ESG in manufacturing industries found it difficult to connect employee engagement themes (qualitative) with measurable sustainability targets like energy efficiency and waste reduction (quantitative) (Mebar, 2024). Studies like Weng (2024) reported parallel results but lacked clear synthesis. Integration through joint displays, meta-inferences, or data transformation was inconsistently applied highlighting a methodological weakness across the field. Without a clear framework for integrating these perspectives, the research struggled to draw meaningful conclusions from the mixed dataset. This highlights the need for more structured methodologies that can effectively bridge quantitative financial analysis with qualitative organizational insights.

4.3.2. Resource-Intensive Nature of MMR

Conducting robust MMR studies is resource-intensive. Lawrence (2024) and Eder & Stampa (2024) noted logistical challenges reduced scope, while Smith (2021) and Fitzsimons & Warren (2024) cited cross-site coordination issues. Limitations were also seen in smaller firms or public sector contexts (e.g., Lengewa, 2024; Duderstadt, 2021). Another major limitation is that MMR is time-consuming and expensive. Collecting, analysing, and integrating multiple data sources requires significant financial resources, technical expertise, and access to reliable ESG data. This challenge is particularly acute in developing regions, where ESG data infrastructure is still evolving. Studies like ElAlfy *et al.* (2025) and Musa (2024) cited challenges related to extended timelines, participant recruitment, and field coordination. These logistical hurdles may deter researchers in LMICs from using MMR without institutional support. A systematic review of ESG investment themes in developing economies found that inconsistent reporting practices and limited data access made MMR particularly difficult to execute (Hadwiger, 2022). Researchers often had to rely on qualitative insights to compensate for missing financial data, which, while valuable, also introduced subjectivity into the analysis.

4.3.3. Lack of Standardized ESG Metrics

A recurrent limitation across the studies was the absence of consistent ESG indicators, hindering dataset integration. This was noted by Shilongo (2023), Kimilu (2021), Abang'a *et al.* (2022), and Ramirez (2023). Zhou & Nian (2024), Fernando *et al.* (2023), and Owilly (2024) also found governance more consistent than environmental or social metrics. Another limitation of MMR in ESG research is the absence of universal ESG measurement standards. There was no consistent use of ESG frameworks. Studies used local guidelines (e.g., NSE Kenya), GRI, or customized ESG indices, making comparisons difficult. This lack of standardization affected the integration of quant data across studies and diminished the comparability of conclusions. ESG reporting frameworks vary significantly across industries, regions, and regulatory bodies, making it challenging to compare results across different studies. For example, research in Southeast Asia found that ESG disclosure requirements varied widely between countries, forcing researchers to rely more on qualitative stakeholder interviews to fill data gaps (Tian *et al.*, 2024). This reliance on contextual narratives rather than standardized indicators made cross-regional comparisons less reliable. The lack of standardized ESG metrics means that mixed-methods studies often struggle to integrate findings in a way that allows for global benchmarking.

4.3.4. Addressing Methodological Gaps in Mixed-Methods ESG Research

Some of the reviewed studies justified the use of MMR, albeit few explicitly. In particular, few studies supported justification for using either sequential or convergent designs (e.g., Mutambik, 2024; Ramirez, 2023; Paranita *et al.*, 2025; Oliveira Pureza, 2020). Yet, several studies integrated qualitative and quantitative approaches but lacked formal design articulation (e.g., Sillanpää, 2020; Oberholzer *et*

al., 2023; Martínez & Poveda, 2022; Abarika & Oboreh, 2024). This highlights the need for more methodological transparency. In summary, MMR provides powerful tools to unpack ESG issues in emerging markets, but more methodological rigour, resourcing and greater harmonisation of core indicators are required to ensure comparability and relevance.

While MMR has clear challenges, these issues are not insurmountable. Researchers and policymakers can enhance the effectiveness and scalability of mixed-methods approaches in ESG by:

- a) Developing standardized frameworks for integrating qualitative and quantitative ESG data. This includes refining models for triangulation and mixed-methods data synthesis.
- b) Leveraging digital tools and AI-driven analytics to streamline ESG data collection and analysis, reducing the resource intensity of MMR.
- c) Encouraging cross-sector collaboration to create more uniform ESG reporting standards, making mixed-methods research more comparable and applicable across industries.

By refining these methodological approaches, MMR can evolve into an even more powerful tool for evaluating and improving corporate sustainability practices. Its ability to combine hard data with real-world insights makes it an indispensable approach for researchers, businesses, and policymakers alike.

4.4. Implications of Methodological Limitations

The absence of standardized ESG metrics across studies significantly influenced both integration and comparability: Zhou & Nian (2024) used domestic Chinese ESG ratings, while Doffour (2022) relied on international indices like Refinitiv yielding divergent insights. Alkaraan *et al.* (2024) and Shilongo (2023) had to reconcile incompatible ESG indicators through thematic interpretation, limiting the reproducibility of findings. This inconsistency not only impairs statistical comparability but often shifts emphasis toward interpretive qualitative inference underscoring the need for standardized metrics tailored to emerging market contexts.

4.5. Conceptual Framework for ESG-MMR in Emerging Markets

To bridge these gaps, the study proposes a contextualized MMR Design framework, mapping context to recommended designs. Figure 3 illustrates the alignment between common ESG research challenges encountered in emerging market contexts and appropriate mixed-methods research (MMR) designs, as identified in the meta-methodological synthesis of reviewed studies.

Figure 3. Mapping Emerging Market ESG Research Challenges to Optimal Mixed-Methods Research (MMR) Designs

This model (illustrated in Figure 2) can guide future researchers in selecting appropriate MMR pathways tailored to ESG environments in the Emerging markets.

5. Conclusions

This study highlights the significance of mixed-methods research (MMR) in deepening the understanding of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices in emerging markets. As the focus on sustainability intensifies globally, mixed-methods research allows scholars to derive more actionable insights into corporate sustainability issues. A quantitative approach helps to determine what changes have occurred, namely whether carbon emissions or return on assets have decreased or increased. A qualitative approach is required to understand why and how such changes happened and examine changes in core practices and their impact on different stakeholders in an organization and the complex negotiation of tensions between stakeholders.

By linking the measurable to the meaningful, MMR allows researchers the opportunity to go beyond skin-deep analyses of ESG performance. Yet, the study suggests that such potential is muted by key challenges: difficulties in data integration, resource intensive multi-strand designs, and a lack of harmonised ESG metrics. If they are not integrated mindfully, MMR findings run the risk of existing as siloed narratives rather than holistic and complete interpretations.

To rectify these shortcomings and challenges, future research should place a priority on developing more explicit frameworks for integrating quantitative and qualitative findings. Strengthening methodological coherence on the data strands will not only increase the validity of MMR studies, but also make their insights more accessible and translatable into practice. Investment in interdisciplinary research teams, in the application of digital tools for data management and visualisation and in stronger cross-institutional support through funding bodies, will be key to scaling high-quality MMR in ESG research. The field also requires universal ESG metrics and stronger guidelines for qualitative data collection. Standardizing ESG metrics can render findings more comparable, replicable, and generalizable within and across industries and geographies, while preserving the depth and richness of context.

Ultimately, MMR provides a powerful methodological tool for producing the rich, multifaceted understanding of ESG practices that neither quantitative nor qualitative methods can achieve alone. By overcoming its methodological and operational challenges, researchers can harness the full potential of MMR to deliver both impactful academic contributions and real-world sustainable change. As ESG considerations continue to influence business practices, regulatory agendas, and societal expectations, the insights obtained through rigorous mixed-methods research will leave an enduring mark on scholarship and practice.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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